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BREAST CANCER – DYNAMICS OF MORBIDITY AND MORTALITY OF THE POPULATION OF THE REPUBLIC OF BELARUS AND THE RUSSIAN FEDERATION

A.S. Aleksandrovich,

Ph.D., Associate professor

T.I. Zimatkina,

Ph.D., Associate professor,

Grodno state medical university,

Grodno

Annotation: The analysis of the current dynamics of morbidity and mortality of the population of the Republic of Belarus and the Russian Federation in connection with breast cancer in recent years has been carried out, as a result of our research, the growth of this disease in the population of the Republic of Belarus and the Russian Federation has been established, which may indicate, on the one hand, a decrease in the level of health and body defenses, and, with on the other hand, about improving the quality of diagnosis of this pathology. The shift of the age peak of the incidence of breast cancer in the female population from 57-61 years to 65-69 years for this period was revealed.

Keywords: breast cancer, morbidity, mortality

РАК МОЛОЧНОЙ ЖЕЛЕЗЫ – ДИНАМИКА ЗАБОЛЕВАЕМОСТИ И СМЕРТНОСТИ НАСЕЛЕНИЯ РЕСПУБЛИКИ БЕЛАРУСЬ И РОССИЙСКОЙ ФЕДЕРАЦИИ

А.С. Александрович,

к.м.н., доц.

Т.И. Зиматкина,

к.б.н., доц.,

Гродненский государственный медицинский университет,

г. Гродно

Аннотация: Проведен анализ современной динамики заболеваемости и смертности населения Республики Беларусь и Российской Федерации в связи с раком молочной железы за последние годы, в результате проведенного нами исследования установлен рост данного заболевания у населения Республики Беларусь и Российской Федерации, что может свидетельствовать, с одной стороны, о снижении уровня здоровья и защитных сил организма, а, с другой стороны, об улучшении качества диагностики данной патологии. Выявлено смещение возрастного пика заболеваемости раком молочной железы женского населения с 57-61 год на 65-69 лет за данный период.

Ключевые слова: рак молочной железы, заболеваемость, смертность

Relevance. Both in the Republic of Belarus and in the Russian Federation, breast cancer occupies a leading position (1-2nd place) in the morbidity and mortality of women from malignant neoplasms. The global average incidence of breast cancer is 43.1 cases per 100 thousand population, of which 74.1 per 100 thousand population or (47.3 %) are in economically developed countries and 31.3 per 100 thousand population (52.7 %) are in developing countries [1-5].

New methods of breast cancer diagnosis and screening are being developed and introduced into clinical practice, however, the morbidity and mortality rates from this pathology continue to grow steadily.

Goal. Analysis of the current dynamics of morbidity and mortality of the population of the Republic of Belarus and the Russian Federation in connection with breast cancer in recent years.

Materials and methods of research. Comparative-evaluative, analytical and epidemiological research methods were used in the work. The materials for the study were data from the state statistical reporting and the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Belarus and the Russian Federation.

Results and their discussion. When studying the epidemiological situation in the Republic of Belarus, it was found that in 1989-2002 the incidence of breast cancer was 46.5 per 100 thousand population (from 35.4 in 1989 to 57.5 cases per 100 thousand population

in 2002). The highest level of malignant neoplasms of the breast was registered in 1989-2002 in the Gomel region (57.3 cases per 100 thousand population). Also significantly higher levels of breast cancer incidence were observed in Minsk (50.5 cases per 100 thousand population) and Vitebsk region (49.6 cases per 100 thousand population). By age, the incidence of this pathology was the highest in the age group of 57-61 years.

The incidence of breast cancer in Russia in the period 1990-2002 increased 1.5 times (from 39.6 in 1990 to 59.5 cases per 100 thousand population in 2002).

In the period 2002-2011, the incidence of breast cancer in the Republic of Belarus increased by 1.33 times (from 57.5 in 2002 to 76.7 cases per 100 thousand population in 2011). It was found that from 2002-2011 in the Russian Federation, this indicator increased by 1.25 times (from 59.5 in 2002 to 74.9 cases per 100 thousand population in 2011). In 2004, the highest incidence rates of breast cancer in the Russian Federation were recorded in the Siberian Federal District (SFD) – 43.61 cases per 100 thousand, which exceeded the all-Russian indicator (40.82), and in 2012.

The incidence of breast cancer in the Republic of Belarus for the period 2011-2017 averaged 82.25 cases per 100 thousand population (from 76.7 in 2011 to 87.8 cases per 100 thousand population in 2017). The number of patients with a first-time diagnosis of breast cancer in 2010-2019 averaged 46.4 per 100 thousand. In 2011-2017, the incidence of breast cancer in the Russian Federation averaged 82.8 cases per 100 thousand population (from 40.3 in 2010 to 52.5 cases per 100 thousand population in 2019).

When studying the distribution of morbidity by age in the Republic of Belarus, it was revealed that the peak of breast cancer in the Republic of Belarus was established in the age group of 65-69 years. The average age of patients diagnosed with this malignant neoplasm in the Russian Federation is 61.5.

When analyzing mortality from this oncological pathology by regions and Minsk, the highest indicator in 2018-2019 was noted among residents of the Vitebsk region (15.7 per 100 thousand population in 2018 and 13.5 per 100 thousand population in 2019), Minsk (12.5 per 100 thousand population in 2018 and 14.0 per 100 thousand population in

2019), Gomel region (12.2 per 100 thousand population in 2018 and 14.6 per 100 thousand population in 2019). In 2018-2019, the mortality rate from breast cancer decreased in the Minsk region by 1.13 times (from 12.7 per 100 thousand population in 2018 and 11.2 per 100 thousand population in 2019). In other areas, an increase in the mortality rate from this pathology was noted.

The long-term dynamics of mortality from breast cancer in 2001-2017 was characterized by a unidirectional moderate downward trend. The mortality rate of women from breast cancer in Belarus in 2001-2017 decreased by 3.5 per 100 thousand population. In 2019, mortality increased by 1.09% compared to 2018 (12.1 cases per 100 thousand population in 2018 and 13.2 cases per 100 thousand population in 2019). It was found that mortality in 2019 was higher in the urban population (13.3 per 100 thousand population) compared to rural by 1.2 times (10.9 per 100 thousand population). It should also be noted an increase of 1.08 times in the mortality of the urban population in the period from 2018-2019 (from 12.3 per 100 thousand population in 2018 to 13.3 per 100 thousand population in 2019) and a decrease in the mortality of the rural population in the same period by 1.02 times (from 11.1 per 100 thousand population in 2018 and 10.9 per 100 thousand population in 2019).

It was found that the dynamics of mortality in the Russian Federation from malignant neoplasms of the breast increased 2.2 times in 1985-2007. It should be noted that the single indicator decreased by 1.34 times in 2007-2018. Over the last 10 years, the average age of the deceased has increased from 65.9 to 67.3 years: for men – from 64.9 to 66.3 years, for women – from 67.0 to 68.5 years. The available data for the Russian Federation and its regions do not yet allow us to fully track the degree of effectiveness of mammographic examinations of the population. However, in a third of the regions of Russia, with an increase in the frequency of mammography, there was a decrease in mortality from this pathology, a pattern characteristic of a significant number of regions of the Central and Siberian Federal Districts. However, another third of the Territories showed a simultaneous increase in the frequency of mammography use and mortality. The largest number of such regions is located in the Volga Federal District.

It is known that the effectiveness of medical care is determined by the number of patients who survived for five years or more after

treatment. At the I-th stage of breast cancer, it is possible to achieve a positive result in 91.8 % of patients, at the II-th stage of the disease – in 64.5 %. The results of treatment are influenced by the results of adjuvant treatment, since mortality in stages I-II is mainly due to the development of distant metastases. It should be noted that some patients with progressive tumors have a positive effect from chemotherapy and hormone therapy and are experiencing a five-year milestone with signs of the disease. In stages III-IV of breast cancer, progression may take the form of both local recurrence and manifest metastases. Some patients with stage III of the disease are experiencing a five-year milestone (42.3 %) due to adjuvant treatment, which allows to increase the duration of remission until the first wave of metastasis. A complete cure in stage IV is almost impossible. However, in some cases it is possible to achieve a partial therapeutic effect and achieve a five-year survival rate in 28.8 % of patients.

Conclusions. As a result of our research, an increase in this disease has been established in the population of the Republic of Belarus and the Russian Federation, which may indicate, on the one hand, a decrease in the level of health and body defenses, and, on the other hand, an improvement in the quality of diagnosis of this pathology. In 2017, the morbidity rate of the population in the Republic of Belarus was 2.5 times higher compared to 1989. The incidence rate in the Russian Federation 1990-2017 increased by 2.2 times. The shift of the age peak of the incidence of breast cancer in the female population from 57-61 years to 65-69 years for this period was revealed. When analyzing mortality from this oncological pathology by regions and Minsk, the highest indicator in 2018-2019 was noted among residents of the Vitebsk region, Minsk, Gomel region. It should also be noted that the mortality rate of the urban population increased by 1.08 times in the period from 2018-2019 in the Republic of Belarus. The dynamics of mortality in the Russian Federation from malignant neoplasms of the breast in 1985-2007. it is characterized by a unidirectional increase, and in the period 2007-2018 by a decrease, which indicates a high development of diagnostic studies.

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